

Creating community-engaged content: Voice and tone

Content is powerful - it can make people feel welcome and excited to engage, or it can alienate and cause them to disengage. The voice and tone of your content matters just as much as its structure and format, and is an important part of how your community or organization is perceived – its “brand identity.”

We think of voice and tone in terms of “climate vs. weather.” Your voice, or the voice of your organization, is the climate – an overarching background presence that pervades everything you do. It describes the way you would like the organization to be consistently perceived, across all of your content - and might reflect some or all of your core values.

Tone, on the other hand is weather – it’s the scattered showers and rainbows of content creation. Tone has more to do with how you would like to make your audience feel in the context of a specific piece of content, and is always supported by your voice.

In this worksheet, we’ll lead you through an exercise to define the voice and tone for your community. Know that your voice may gradually shift over time, but it will stay broadly recognizable over the lifetime of your community. Tone is considerably more changeable, and may vary depending on the different member types or audiences you engage with. You might even see subtle variations in each piece of content you create.

We developed this activity for our Content Design (CODE) course, a six-week online training that introduces a strategic approach to designing and creating community-engaged content. For more information about the course, including when it will run next and to access related guidebooks on community-engaged content, [please visit the course webpage](#).

Voice

We'll start by defining your community's voice. You can do this on your own or with your colleagues, depending on how much time you have to devote to the activity. If you do the activity with colleagues, steps 2 and 3 should be done separately by each person taking part and then you work together in step 4 onwards. You might also consider revisiting the activity every few months or so or as people rotate on and off your team.

STEP 1: SET UP YOUR ADJECTIVE BANK

In the appendix of this worksheet, you'll find a template adjective bank. The first thing you need to do is either copy and paste these adjectives into an editable document, or print it out. If you're printing the doc, you'll also need a pen or highlighter for the next step.

STEP 2: CHOOSE YOUR TOP 10-12 ADJECTIVES

With your highlighter or pen, whether they are physical or virtual, go through the adjective bank and highlight any words that describe the voice of your community. Try not to choose too many adjectives. If you find that you've highlighted more than 15, attempt to narrow things down a little.

STEP 3: CREATE 3 CLUSTERS OF ADJECTIVES

At the bottom of your doc, or on the back of your piece of paper, now try to cluster similar words together. The goal here is to tease out what is the root meaning in these clusters, and narrow down the adjectives that describe your community at its core.

STEP 4: DECIDE ON THE 3 WORDS THAT DESCRIBE YOUR VOICE

This is where it's particularly interesting to compare your answers with others on your team. It's likely that some of your words will overlap, or perhaps you've chosen words that mean similar things but the nuance of how they are different will help you align around your voice.

Once you've decided on your three words, write them down on a sticky note or pin them at the top of your team Slack channel. These words will guide every piece of content you create from now on.

Tone

You can perform the same exercise for tone as for voice, however your tone will shift depending on the kind of content you're making. The most manageable way to start with this is to consider your different member and/or audience types. However, if you know you have a particularly strategic piece of content to share, e.g., a blog post about a price increase, it may be worth considering the tone on a content item by content item basis. We've created a table below for you to fill in with the various types of content, and suggested a couple of examples to get you started.

Community voice: _____, _____, & _____.

Member type or Audience	Tone
<i>New community members</i>	<i>Welcoming, connected, reassuring</i>
<i>External stakeholders</i>	<i>Professional, knowledgeable, productive</i>

Appendix: Adjective bank

This adjective bank can be added to or edited to meet your needs. Let us know what words you've added or removed by emailing info@cscce.org!

academic	comfortable	enthusiastic
actionable	confident	evidence-based
adventurous	considerate	excitable
applicable	consistent	excited
ambitious	courageous	extroverted
anticipatory	creative	exuberant
artistic	credible	faithful
aspirational	curious	fantastic
assertive	deliberate	fast-paced
authoritative	demanding	firm
beautiful	dependable	friendly
brave	determined	fun
brief	distinct	future-facing
bright	dogmatic	glamorous
calm	driven	good-natured
caring	eager	gregarious
cautious	elegant	happy
charismatic	empowering	helpful
charming	enabling	human
cheerful	encouraging	inclusive
clear	energetic	important
clever	engaging	impulsive

industrious	persuasive	sincere
informative	playful	slow
integrated	pleasant	sociable
intelligent	polite	sparkling
intentional	practical	supportive
intimidating	pragmatic	swift
introspective	proactive	sympathetic
inventive	professional	thoughtful
inviting	quantitative	traditional
joyful	rapid	transparent
kind	reassuring	trustworthy
knowledgeable	reliable	unusual
loyal	relieved	valuable
modern	research-driven	welcoming
open-ended	respectful	wise
opinionated	responsive	wistful
passive	serious	witty
perfectionist	short	youthful

Citing and reusing this worksheet

CITATION AND REUSE

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Cite as: Center for Scientific Collaboration and Community Engagement. (2025) Creating community-engaged content: Voice and tone. Pratt and Woodley doi: [10.5281/zenodo.15700485](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15700485)

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Last updated June 2025